

Seroprevalence of hepatitis b markers among blood donors at the yaounde gynaecology obstetrics and pediatrics hospital

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Abstract

Hepatitis B virus infection (HBV) remains a significant global health concern. Although technics are in place to reduce the risk of transmission, the increased presence of HBV among blood donors in africa, particularly in Cameroon, there is a risk of transmission through transfusion despite the presence of an HBSAg screening algorithm in blood banks. The aim of this study was to highlight the seroprevalence of hepatitis B markers among blood donors at the Yaounde gynaecology obstetrics and paediatrics hospital.

A prospective cross-sectionnal and analytical study was conducted among blood donors at the Yaounde gynaecology obstetrics and paediatrics hospital over a four month period from June to March 2025. Socio-demographic data were collected using survey forms. The search for anti-HBc and anti-HBs antibodies was carried out using rapid diagnostic tests and confirmed by the ELISA method. Statistical tests were performed using SPSS 2022 software, and graphical tables were created using Microsoft word 2019 and Microsoft excel 2019 software.

The 200 blood donors selected, we found seroprevalence rates of 13,50% for HBsAg, 43,4% for anti-HBc and 16,2% for anti-HBs with associated risk factors such as age, gender, marital status, and unprotected sexual intercourse.

This study shows that transfusion safety remains a significant issues due to the circulation of these infectious markers among family and replacement donors, most of whom discovered their serological status late during a blood donation. It is therefore strongly recommended that HbcAb and/or HbsAb be tested for during the biological qualification of blood donations.

Keywords: Seroprevalence; Hepatitis B; Transfusion risk; Blood donors; Blood infection

1. Introduction

The hepatitis B virus is actually the smallest double-stranded DNA virus known to infect humans (1). It consists of three major structures: the envelope, which includes the surface antigen (HBsAg) ; the capsid or core, which includes the HBcAg ; and the nucleus (2). According to the world health organisation (WHO), approximately 250 million people worldwide are living with hepatitis B, and 1.1 million deaths was expected in 2022 (3). The prevalence of hepatitis B is very high in china and sub-saharan Africa, where 70-95% of residents have already had hepatitis B ; Europe and Nord

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America remain areas of low endemicity with 3-5% of residents having had hepatitis B (4). The prevalence in Cameroon is 11.2% (5), with hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection remaining the most significant form of infection through transfusion (6). In 95% of cases, people who contract the HBV eliminate it without symptoms in the case of acute hepatitis, which lasts only few weeks (7). If HBsAg is still detectable after 6 months, the condition is considered chronic hepatitis B (2), these individuals are systematically rejected when they give blood in order to avoid any risk of contamination during a blood transfusion. However, the absence of AgHBs detection does not rule out the circulation of infectious particles in the blood. According to several studies, a so-called silent or occult HBV infection is possible and very often goes unnoticed, which raises significant problems in cases of blood transfusions and transplants. Occult hepatitis B (OBI) is largely overlooked due to the fact that hepatitis B detection relies on the presence of HBsAg (8). A study conducted at the Laquintinie hospital blood bank in Douala revealed an overall seroprevalence of HBcAb of 57% among blood donors who tested negative for HBsAg (9). Simultaneous testing for the three markers HBsAg, HBcAb, HBsAb make it possible to determine whether or not there is a risk of infection and can provide an indication of the stage of infection (10). The objective of this study was to highlight the seroprevalence of hepatitis B markers among blood donors at the Yaounde gynaecology obstetrics and paediatrics hospital.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Type, location and period of study

This was a prospective cross-sectionnal and analytical study which we carried out on family and replacement blood donors at the Yaounde gynaecology obstetrics and paediatrics hospital over a four-month period from June to March 2025.

2.2. Sampling and administrative procedures

We collected and analysed a total of 200 samples from blood donors aged between 21 and 40 years. We subsequently obtained collection autorisation from the HGOPY ethics committee, as well as ethical clearance N5064CEI-Udo/07/2025/M from the ethics and institutional committee of the university of Douala.

2.3. Methodology

Survey forms were used to collect data such as age, gender, marital status, number of partners and unprotected sexual intercourse. After collecting whole blood in dry tubes, the various samples were centrifuged and AgHBs was determined using the Easycheks rapid diagnostic test. We collected the different sera and stored them in eppendorf tubes in a freezer at -20°C before later performing ELISA tests to confirm the AgHBs results using the Fortress one step reagent and to detect HBcAb and HBsAb using Atlas medical and Sharlonilabs reagents in all AgHBs negative samples. The sensitivity and specificity of the previous tests ranged from 99% to 100%.

2.4. Statistical analysis

Statistical tests were performed using SPSS 2022 software, and graphical tables were created using Microsoft word 2019 and Microsoft excel 2019 software.

3. Results

In our study of 200 bloods donors, males were in the majority with a rate of 90.5%, the male/female ratio was 0.67%, and the average age was 29± 27 years. Unprotected sexual intercourse, age, and marital status were significantly associated with the presence of hepatitis B antibodies. Twenty-seven (27) blood donors tested positive for AgHBs. The search for markers revealed the seroprevalence of 13,50% for HBsAg, 43,4% for anti-HBc and 16,2% for anti-HBs.

Table 1 Seroprevalence of hepatitis B markers

Hepatitis B Markers	Positive	Negative
HBs Antigen	27(13.5%)	173(86.5%)
HBc Antibody	75(43.4%)	98(59.6%)
HBs Antibody	28(16.2%)	145(83.8%)

4. Discussion

Our study was conducted over a four-month period from March to June 2025, during which we collected 200 samples from blood donors at the HGOPY. The aim was to determine the seroprevalence of hepatitis B markers among blood donors. The studied population was predominantly male, with a representative rate of 90.5%, this results was similar to several studies, including taht of Goita and *al.* which obtained a significantly similar rate of 94.36% (11), this could be explained by the fact men have fewer physiological constraints that women (pregnancy, breastfeeding, menstruation). The age of blood donors ranged from 21 to 40 years old, with an average of 29 ± 27 years, Sarr and *al.* found an average age of 26 years with an age range ≤ 20 years (12), meaning that the donor population was particularly young.

Our statistical analyses showed a significant link between the age group [40-60 years] for HBcAb positivity, suggesting more frequent exposure to the hepatitis B virus in this age group. Our results are similar to those obtained by Fopa in Cameroon, who, in his work in the same context, reported a very high rate of this antibody in the 41-50 age group (13). These results differ from those obtained by Traoré Nahawa in Burkina Faso, where the 25-44 age group tested positive for the same marker (14). No more age group showed significant differences for the other markers. The marital status of blood donors was represented overwhelmingly by single people, with a rate of 81%, our results are very similar to those of Ayamekpé and *al.*, who noted a rate of 82% (15). No significant association was found between marital status and the presence of HBsAg, married subjects showed high positivity for HBcAb with no HBsAb, which could suggest weaker immunity in this population, but this cannot be formally concluded. However, the study conducted by Koné in Mali in the same context showed a seroprevalence of 40,3% for HBsAg among married people (7).

Volunteer donors were very poorly represented 2%, unlike family and replacement blood donors 98% ; these results are comparable to those of Diarra and *al.* who reported a rate of 73.69% for family and replacement donors (16), but contrary to the study by Ouattara and *al.* which had a higher rate of 63.92% for volunteer donors (17). This situation can be explained in our context by the fact that voluntary donation is still slightly known among the general population, it is not yet sufficiently ingrained in the culture and it is rejected by certain religions, or simply poorly perceived in local customs.

In order to determine the presence of a risk of infection due to the transmission of viral hepatitis B among blood donors at HGOPY, we then tested for HBsAg using the ELISA immunoassay method. These tests yielded the following results : 13,50%, 43,4%, 16,2%, these rates are similar to those obtained by Pawlotsky *et al.*, whose seroprevalence was 14% for HBsAg, but differ from his results for HBsAb, which was 89% (18), the work carried out by kegne shows a rate of 49% (6), which is similar to the rate we obtained for HBcAb, this seroprevalence is slightly lower than that of Biwolé and *al.*, which was 56.57% in a similar study at the laquintinie Hospital in Douala (9).

Our results also indicate that 31.21% of the blood donors were HBcAb positive with the absence of HBsAb, this may be due either to a failure of the immune system or to the fact that the infection is still in its early stages, in which case HBsAg has not yet been detected. They are therefore considered potentially dangerous. The simultaneous presence of these two antibodies demonstrates immunity acquired after contact with HBV, given that only two donors had received the hepatitis B vaccine. All the above factors indicate a risk of transmission of infectious diseases through transfusion, particularly in the case of hepatitis B, for which infection markers remain particularly high. It would therefore be important to include other screening tests in order to limit the number of potential blood donors who could transmit hepatitis B infection.

5. Conclusion

This study shows that transfusion safety remains a significant issue due to the circulation of these infectious markers among blood donors, who are still mainly family and replacement donors, most of whom discover their serological status late during a blood donation. It is therefore strongly recommended that HBcAb and/or HBsAb be tested for during the biological qualification of blood donations.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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